

SMART 05

Calendars, Alarms and Maps

Using apps on a mobile device to organise your day and find your way.

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of Technology

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SMART MODULE 5

Calendars, alarms and maps

This module covers some of the more advanced uses of a mobile phone that can be useful in organising your day. The “Calendar”, “Clock” and “Google Maps” apps are very useful to help you remember appointments and find your way to them.

Intended audience

This module is intended for those who have confidently mastered the content in the earlier practical modules of **SMART 02: Making And Receiving Calls With A Smartphone** and **SMART 03: How To Communicate By Text With A Smartphone** and are interested in what a mobile device can do for you when you are travelling and meeting people.

This module adopts a hands-on approach and looks at different ways of using three useful types of apps; the “Calendar” and the “Clock” for organising your time and the “Google Maps” app for helping you on journeys.

This module assumes you are using an Android™ device.

What will you learn in this module

- 1 How the “Calendar” app can help you with reminders and alarms.
- 2 How to set and use an alarm or timer using the “Clock” app.
- 3 About keeping track of different time zones using the “Clock” app.
- 4 Using “Google Maps” for facilitating wayfinding.

Chapters in this module

1

Using calendars and reminders on a mobile device

2

Using alarms, timers and world clocks on a mobile device

3

Using “Google Maps” for wayfinding

SMART

MODULE 5

CHAPTER 1

Using calendars and reminders on a mobile device

This chapter explains how to use the “Calendar” application on your mobile device. You can use the “Calendar” app to set reminders for dates of meetings, appointments or birthdays so that your phone will remind you when the event is coming up.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 How to find the “Calendar” app.
- 2 What does the “Calendar” app look like.
- 3 How to add an event (reminder).
- 4 How to navigate and edit events.
- 5 What happens when the event occurs.

Uses of adding events and viewing calendar

You can use the “Calendar” app to tell what day it will be on a certain date, and also, to set events to remind you of special occasions or any important days in the future.

You can also use it to insert alerts for regularly occurring events, such as weekly appointments with a physiotherapist, or one-off event reminders, like a visit to the doctor or a meeting with friends. You can add events weeks in advance and the app can act as a reminder.

Finding the “Calendar” app

The “Calendar” app can usually be found on your home screen with the “Calendar” icon.

It is important to note that the icon for the “Calendar” app can be in different colours on different devices.

Process

1

2

3

Opening the “Calendar” app

After finding the “Calendar” app icon on your home screen, tap the icon.

This will lead you to the main page of the “Calendar” app, usually showing today’s date as shown here.

Process

Navigating within the “Calendar” app

To add a new event, tap on the day and then tap the time that you wish to add the event.

Finally, tap on the “+” sign at the bottom left of the screen to create the event.

Process

1

2

3

Editing the event (reminder)

As shown in the image, this will take you to a page where you can edit the event.

You can use this screen to add extra information and then create your new event.

Process

Editing the event (reminder)

You can change the name of the event, for example, if you have an important meeting or appointment.

Process

Editing the event (reminder)

Adding a location for an event is optional, but sometimes it is useful to remember where it is happening.

First, you need to swipe up to reach the location box, then tap it to enter a location name.

Process

Editing the event (reminder)

Choose “On that day at 08:00” to get a reminder of the event.

You can also change the “Reminder time” at the bottom of the screen to suit your routine.

Process

Submit the event

Finally, tap on the “✓” button to save the event.

Process

Navigating the “Calendar” app with an event

You can now see that the saved event is visible on the main “Calendar” page.

When you tap the event, the details will be shown and you can edit them again if you wish.

Process

When the event time occurs

On the day of the event, your mobile device will give you a notification at the specific time that you chose when editing the event details. Once you see the reminder you can close it or snooze it.

Process

10

Deleting an event

To delete an event, simply tap on the event on the main "Calendar" page. Then tap the trashcan button "🗑️" to delete it.

Do the task!

Teresa would like to add a doctor's appointment to the "Calendar" app on her phone. Can you help?

- Meet and get to know Teresa. [You can find information about Teresa here.](#)
- Teresa would like to enter a calendar alert for an important doctor's appointment, next Thursday at 10 am.
- On your mobile device use the "Calendar" app to put in an appointment that Teresa.
- Add a reminder for Teresa at 8 am on Thursday.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 5** **CHAPTER 1** Using calendars and reminders on a mobile device

Where is the "Calendar" app normally found?

- In the "Google Apps" screen
- On the home screen
- In the configuration menu

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

How to use the “Calendar” app on your mobile phone.

2

How to add an event to your calendar.

3

How to edit and delete events.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 5

CHAPTER 2

Using alarms, timers and world clocks

In this chapter, you are going to learn all about creating and using alarms, timers, and the world clock on your mobile device. These features can be useful in many situations for reminders and organising your daily life.

What will you learn in this chapter

1 How to create and use alarms.

2 How to use timers.

3 How to use the stopwatch.

4 How to use world clocks.

How to create and edit alarms

Alarms on the phone are just like those on your alarm clock but with more features.

The “Clock” app allows you to have multiple alarms active at one time.

It is simpler to use than the “Calendar” app and can be useful for setting daily or short-term reminder alarms.

How to create and edit alarms

It is very useful to be able to set alarms, whether it is to set a routine in your daily life, such as daily medication reminders or to use just once.

Let's look at the steps involved in doing that.

Finding the “Clock” app!

It can be a bit of a challenge to find the “Clock” app at first. The “Clock” app is typically located on the home screen. It can sometimes be found by tapping on the “Tools” folder on your home screen.

The “Clock” app icon is generally a clock face or alarm clock icon. Tap on it to open and access its features.

Process

1

2

3

Opening alarms in the “Clock” app

Once you're in the “Clock” app, at the top of the screen you will see 4 icons; one for each function of the “Clock” app. The one on the left “🕒” is the “Alarm” icon. Tap it and it will turn the blue colour as shown here when selected.

Process

1

2

3

Create a new alarm

To create a new alarm, tap on the “+” icon at the bottom of the screen.

Process

1

2

3

Editing the alarm

You can now slide up and down on the hour and minute controls for the alarm to select the alarm time.

Note: The time is in 24-hour format.

Process

Alarm settings

After setting the time, you can set the alarm to repeat on certain days by tapping on the “Repeat” text below the time. You can set the alarm tone by tapping on “Ringtone” and tapping on one of the alarm tones. By tapping on “Label” you can name the alarm.

Process

Save the alarm

Tap on the “✓” button in the top right corner of the screen to save the alarm.

Multiple alarms

Having more than one alarm can be very useful. You might want an alarm to wake you up at 8 am and a second alarm at 8:45 am as a reminder to leave your house by 9 am to catch the public transport.

You can set multiple alarms in the alarm tab by tapping on the toggle button beside the alarm you wish to turn on. An alarm is turned on if the toggle button is blue “”.

To turn off an alarm, tap the toggle button again. The toggle button should turn grey “” which indicates that the alarm is now off.

Stopping an alarm

When an alarm goes off, a large circular button in the middle of the screen allows you to “Snooze” and swiping up some white text turns off the alarm.

By tapping “Snooze”, the alarm will stop for 10 minutes before going on again.

You can also “Swipe up to turn off” the alarm completely.

Do the task!

Teresa would like to add an alarm for 8:15 am each morning on her mobile device. Can you help?

- Meet and get to know Teresa. [You can find information about Teresa here.](#)
- Teresa would like to set a repeating daily alarm for 8:15 am each morning.
- On your mobile device use the “Clock” app to enter an alarm call for that time.
- Actually she has changed her mind. Please, change the time of the daily alarm to 8:20 am.

Do the task!

Teresa would like to add a medication reminder for her husband on her mobile device. Can you help?

- Meet and get to know Teresa. [You can find information about Teresa here.](#)
- Teresa's husband has multiple chronic conditions. He takes his medication in two parts; each morning at 9:30 am and again at 10:45 pm.
- On your mobile device use the alarm feature of the "Clock" app to put in two daily medication reminders that Teresa would use.

Using timers

Using timers can be a helpful way to control the time required for an activity. It works similarly to a physical timer.

Timers can be useful, for example, when cooking and baking or for timing some wellness activities, such as bathing your feet, meditating, or even reminding yourself to stretch or take a break when you are concentrating.

Process

1

2

3

Opening the “Clock” app to create a timer

Let's begin with making a timer. The first step is to open the “Clock” app, which was shown earlier. On most phones, the “Clock” icon is an analogue clock and the word “Clock” is written below.

Tap the “Clock” icon to enter the app!

Process

1

2

3

Setting the duration of the “Timer”

Once you're in the “Clock” app, the first thing to do is select the timer. At the top of the screen, 4 icons are describing the functions. The right icon shaped like an hourglass “🕒” is the “Timer” icon.

Tap it and it will turn blue when selected.

Process

1

2

3

Setting the duration of the “Timer” - continued

There are three dials in the centre of the screen for hours, minutes and seconds, ordered in the classic clock format.

To set the duration of the “Timer”, swipe your finger up on the screen to increase the number of hours and swipe down to decrease them. Repeat for the minute and second dials.

Process

Setting the alert sound

To choose an alert sound tap on the 3 dots in the top right-hand corner of the screen.

This will open the configuration menu with a list of sounds that can be chosen.

If you prefer, you can also skip this step and use the default sound.

Process

Starting the “Timer”

Finally, to start the “Timer”, tap on the blue “▶” (Play) button at the bottom centre of the screen.

Process

Cancel or pause the “Timer”

When the “Timer” is running, you’ll see the time counting down in big text on the screen.

You can stop or pause the “Timer” at any time by tapping on the blue “■” (Stop) or “||” (Pause) buttons located at the bottom of the display.

Stopwatch: an aid for making calendar alerts

The “Stopwatch” tab, another feature of the “Clock” app, works in a very similar way to the timer, but it measures how long it takes to do a certain task. In this case, you start a “Timer” and then stop it when the task is completed.

For example, the stopwatch could be used to figure out how long it takes, walking at a normal pace, to reach the train station or bus stop and buy a ticket. This information could be useful when deciding when to leave the house to catch public transport on time.

Do the task!

António wishes to do an antigen test. Can you help him to use the “Timer” features to time his test?

- Meet and get to know António. [You can find information about António here.](#)
- António is testing himself for COVID using an antigen test kit, and it is written on the instructions that he needs to set a timer for 15 minutes to know when the test will be finished.
- Use the “Clock” app on your mobile device to set a timer for 15 minutes.
- Can you think of other good uses for the “Clock” app’s “Timer” feature?

Uses for the “World Clock”

The “World Clock” tells you what time it is, anywhere in the world.

It can be very useful if you have family living abroad. It will tell you what time it is at the place they are.

It is also very useful if you are travelling and get in touch with your family back home. Using the “World Clock” you will know what time it is there.

Process

1

2

3

Opening the “Clock” app to create a “World Clock”

Let's start creating a “World Clock”. The first step is to open the “Clock” app as before.

Tap the “Clock” icon to enter the app.

Process

1

2

3

Select the “World Clock” icon

In the “Clock” app, select the “World Clock” icon from the top of the screen. There are 4 icons. The second from the left, the icon looking like a clock “🕒”, is the “World Clock” icon.

Tap the “World Clock” icon. It will turn blue when selected.

Process

1

2

3

Adding a “World Clock”

To add a “World Clock”, tap the blue “+” button at the bottom of the screen.

Process

Choosing a location

Now select the location from where you want to know the time.

You can search for a city by tapping the grey search bar at the top and then typing the name of the city.

Once you have found the city you are looking for, tap the name of the city to add its “World Clock”.

Note: If the city you're looking for does not appear, try searching for a nearby city.

Process

Viewing the time

You can now see the time in the city you added on the “World Clock” page.

You can add as many cities as you like.

Process

Deleting a “World Clock”

To delete a “World Clock”, first select the world clock you want to delete. Tap the “World Clock” and the “✓” icon will turn blue when selected.

Then tap the “🗑️” (Trash) button at the bottom of the screen.

Do the task!

Cornelia would like to use her “Clock” app to know what time it is where her sons live. Can you help?

- Meet and get to know Cornelia. [You can find information about Cornelia here.](#)
- Teresa’s sons live abroad, one in Kuala Lumpur and another in New York, and she finds it difficult to keep track of when they are each likely to be available for a WhatsApp call.
- On your mobile device use the “Clock” app to set up a “World Clock” for Kuala Lumpur and another one for New York.

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 5** **CHAPTER 2** Using alarms, timers and world clocks

The "Clock" app allows you to have more than one alarm active at one time.

- true
- false

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

1

In this chapter, you learnt how to create and use alarms.

2

You learnt how to use timers and stopwatches.

3

You learnt how to use world clocks to view the time anywhere in the world.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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SMART

MODULE 5

CHAPTER 3

Using “Google Maps” for wayfinding

In this chapter, you are going to learn how to use the “Google Maps” app for wayfinding. There are a number of maps apps but we will focus on the “Google Maps” app that is commonly used on Android™ devices. You can apply the process shown here to maps apps on iOS devices. Different features on the app will also be introduced.

What will you learn in this chapter

- 1 How to open "Google Maps".
- 2 How to search for a destination on "Google Maps".
- 3 How to select the type of transport that will be used.
- 4 How to select route options.
- 5 How to choose the fastest route.
- 6 How to follow the navigation.

Wayfinding apps like “Google Maps”

Mobile devices have effectively replaced paper maps.

“Google Maps” is an example of an advanced application that allows users to find their way to different locations throughout their environment.

It is very popular today because, with one tap of a finger, the user can find out how to get to a location, the public transportation available and the time of the journey.

Moreover, the users can select the best route to take and can even add intermediate stops.

Downloading “Google Maps”

“Google Maps” is already installed on most Android™ phones. The icon is usually either on the home screen or in the Google folder that you can open from the home screen. If it is not installed, you can install it using Google Play. Installation is like the process of installing “WhatsApp”. See modules **SMART 02** and **SMART 03**.

Open “Google Play” by tapping on the icon and then:

- Type “Google Maps” in the search bar on top,
- Tap the “” (Search) icon,
- Select, for example, “Google Maps” from the proposed list and
- Select “Install”.

Starting “Google Maps”

Normally, after downloading an application, it goes straight to your home screen or into an app folder on the home screen together with other Google apps.

So after downloading “Google Maps”, you should be able to see it on the home screen or the Google apps folder of your phone.

The “Google Maps” icon looks like a multicoloured inverted drop, such as the one on the image on the right.

Did you know?

You can add a photo or edit information to help keep the map up to date with the latest details.

Allowing “Google Maps” to use your GPS

The Global Positioning System, or GPS, is a satellite navigation system that provides location, velocity, and time synchronization. This is needed to maximise “Google Maps” functionality.

Before proceeding to use “Google Maps”, you have to allow the app to use your GPS if you wish route descriptions based on your own location. You will be sharing personal data. You may wish to look back at module **SMART 04: Personal mobile security**, to decide whether you agree to do that.

Process

1

2

3

Open settings

Swipe downwards on the home screen and then tap the cog icon “” shown here to perform some settings.

Process

1

2

3

Find location in settings

Scroll down through settings until you see "Location".
Open "Location" by tapping on it.

Process

1

2

3

Switch on location access

Under "allow apps to access location", slide the "Location access" slider toggle from "Off" to "On". Now apps, including "Google Maps", can use information about your location to provide a better service. If you don't like that your location is known, you can switch it off in the same way.

"Google Maps" - Overview

"Google Maps" is an easy yet very complex application that allows users to simply enter a location into the search bar and quickly responds with a way of getting there and the exact time it would take for you to reach your destination.

"Google Maps" allows the user to choose the mode of transport, i.e. driving, public transport (bus, train, etc.), walking or taxi. Based upon what mode the user chooses the application provides the approximate travel time and the costs whether that's the bus fare or taxi cost.

Wayfinding using “Google Maps”

You will now learn about the basic steps of wayfinding using “Google Maps”.

Process

1

2

3

Opening the "Google Maps" app

In order to use the "Google Maps" app, you need to open it by tapping the "Google Maps" icon, which looks like a multicoloured inverted drop.

So, the first step is to tap the icon.

Process

1

2

3

Starting your navigation

After opening the "Google Maps" app, tap the "Route" button (a blue square with a white route icon) to choose the destination for your trip.

Process

1

2

3

Choosing the start and end locations for your trip

Enter the start and end locations for your trip. For example, choose your current location as a starting point and a restaurant as your destination.

While you're typing, "Google Maps" will show suggestions, which you can tap to select.

Once you've entered your start and end locations, "Google Maps" will show you navigation options.

Process

4

5

6

Choosing your mode of transport

"Google Maps" can provide you with different route options depending on the mode of transport you want to use. The different modes of transport can be accessed by tapping one of the icons near the top of the screen:

- The "Car" for driving
- The "Train" icon for public transport
- The "Walking person" for walking
- The "Person with the raised hand and a briefcase" for taxi or
- The "Bicycle" for cycling.

In the example, the "Car" is highlighted in blue, as driving is selected by default. Tap your preferred mode of transport.

Process

4

5

6

View different modes of transport

When tapping on another mode of transport, "Google Maps" will automatically give you the fastest route.

Choosing walking as a mode of transport will show you recommended routes to walk including pedestrian shortcuts.

Process

4

5

6

Getting directions

Once you have chosen your preferred mode of transport and route, tap the "Start" button on the bottom of the screen.

Process

Start navigating

"Google Maps", by default, will show you the fastest route to get to your destination with a description of all steps.

Follow the route on the screen.

Do the task!

António will visit a new local cafe today. Can you help him to get to the appointment?

- Meet and get to know António. [You can find information about António here.](#)
- António has heard of a new café that is close to his home. Now he can travel by wheelchair, but he doesn't know the way.
- On your mobile device, think of the name of a cafe near António and use “Google Maps” to find a way to reach it on foot.
- Add it to your favourite places in the “Google Maps” app, so you can easily find it later.

Did you know?

Voice guidance is also a feature of “Google Maps”. That means it can give you directions verbally so you would not need to look at your screen as much, especially when you’re driving.

Quote

“This application is great, I am able to see different places in the world in a very simple way and from the comfort of my home. I also really like the ability to calculate time and also indicate directions, which allows me to plan trips and you know approximately how long it will take to arrive.”

Laura Noda

Vice President, Amazon Logistics

Quiz

Click the **Quiz** button to edit this object

 SMART **MODULE 5** **CHAPTER 3** Using "Google Maps" for wayfinding

Google Maps can help you to find your way to a place you have never been before.

true

false

Chapter summary

1

This chapter has described how to use “Google Maps” on Android™ devices.

2

The knowledge gained allows you to find your way to specific locations – even in unfamiliar places.

3

You will be able to use “Google Maps” efficiently and arrive at different locations without stress.

Chapter completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this chapter!

Summary of acquired skills

- 1 In this chapter, you have learned how to use "Google Maps" for wayfinding.
- 2 You have learned how to use different features on "Google Maps".

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this chapter or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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Module summary

1

You can use a mobile device to avoid forgetting important commitments.

2

You have learnt how to use a “Calendar” app to put reminders for important dates.

3

You have learnt how to use the timer feature of the “Clock” app to enter alarms.

4

Your mobile device can also be a great help in getting to unknown places.

5

You have learnt about “Google Maps”, and how to use it to find your way to a location.

6

You have learned how these apps could be useful for organising your day.

7

There are other features of the “Calendar”, “Clock” and “Google Maps” apps. Please try them out!

8

You can now move on to the next module **SMART 06: Wearable Technology**.

Module completed!

Congratulations! You have successfully completed this module!

Summary of acquired skills

1

You have learnt how to be reminded of appointments by the “Calendar” app.

2

You have learnt about the “Clock” app and setting alarms on a mobile device.

3

You have learnt about “Google Maps” and how to use it for wayfinding.

What is next?

Now you can either repeat this module or follow our study recommendation by clicking on one of the buttons below:

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